

DELAMINATION DEFECTS IN CFRP COMPOSITES: HIGH FREQUENCY ULTRASONICS TO VISUALISE THE THIRD DIMENSION

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ABSTRACT

Delaminations have a very large influence on the residual (especially compressive) properties of composite laminates. Therefore non-destructive evaluation techniques must be available to visualize the delaminated regions with the highest possible resolution. With the exact knowledge of the extent and depth (between which layers) of a delamination, further modelling of its influence on the properties is possible. High frequency ultrasonics can be used with a high degree of resolution (lateral and axial) and reproducibility. A computer program was developed to process the ultrasonic reflections obtained in a C-scan to end up with quasi-three-dimensional plots of the damage present in the laminates.

Keywords: ultrasonics, high frequency, cfrp composites, delaminations

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of composite materials in safety-critical engineering structures requires the development of non-destructive techniques which can quantify the damage state of the material. Probably the most significant flaw that can occur in a composite material is a delamination. Delaminations, which often form the second stage of damage development after matrix cracking, can be the end-of-life for critical structures when the size is greater than a specified minimum. However, it is also important to know between which load-carrying plies of the composite laminate the delaminations are situated to account properly for their criticality.

High frequency ultrasonics using a focused transducer/receiver can be used to make a thorough study of the delaminations in composite laminates. Carrying out a C-scan and measuring for each scan point the time of flight of the major reflections gives the basic data for a quasi-3D presentation of the damage present in the composite laminate. The X-ray radiography tech-

nique (when needed penetrant enhanced) was used to compare the results obtained with the high frequency ultrasonic C-scan technique.

2. SPECIMEN CHOICE

Carbon fibre reinforced epoxy laminates, Fibredux 920 C-TS-5-50% and HTA/6376, with artificial defects or with defects induced due to mechanical loading (impact) were used for this study. The laminate lay-up was $(0^\circ, 90^\circ)_4$ for the $10 \times 10 \text{ cm}^2$ plate with square Tygavac foil (vacuum bag) inserts at each corner at different depths and $(\pm 45^\circ, 90^\circ, 0^\circ)_5$ for the impacted $10 \times 15 \text{ cm}^2$ plate.

3. EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

The *high frequency ultrasonic C-scan equipment* used for this research consists of modules of the HF broadband US-system, HFUS 2000, developed by Dr. Hillger, Ingenieurbüro Dr.-Ing. W. Hillger (Braunschweig), namely the pulser/preamplifier HFUS 2011 module, the electronic switch for amplification and filter channel HFUS 2023, the main amplifier HFUS 2024 and two gates HFUS module 2060 and 2061. Further instruments are a LeCroy 9400A oscilloscope, a Unidex UD11 motion controller, a personal computer and a 50 MHz PVDF-foil transducer/receiver, IAP-FS 50.2.1 of Krautkrämer Co.

This HF-broadband-ultrasonic system (up to 80 MHz) is characterized by its high axial resolution and the high dynamic range of the amplifier. For this noise-free broadband amplifiers with a short recovery time after saturation (f.i. by the first echo reflection) are needed. The system also has a high output-voltage and a short pulse-rise time of the pulser. This is needed to find small defects in strongly attenuating materials. The pulser/preamplifier is located in a separate housing and positioned close to the pulser/receiver in order to reduce the signal attenuation by cable capacity and the high frequency noise signals. The 50 MHz PVDF-foil transducer/receiver has a focal spot of $250 \mu\text{m}$, a focal length of 25 mm and the working distance ranges from 18.5 to 41 mm.

The ultrasonic data were taken using a computer-controlled highly stable scanning system. The step size during a scan may be set as small as 0.037 mm. For the ultrasonic C-scan operation two procedures can be followed. The *first procedure* makes a histogram of the time of flight for each reflection detected from the composite plate under investigation. Depending on this histogram the operator can choose between an automatic or manual process to obtain a quasi-three-dimensional plot of the C-scan information. The automatic process will make, depending on the time of flight between the front- and backwall reflection of the plate and the number of layers of the composite plate, a choice of equidistant intervals in which the amplitu-

des of the reflections will be used to form the quasi-3D-plot. In the manual procedure the operator chooses those intervals which no longer have to be equidistant.

For the *second procedure* a reference point on the composite plate is taken and from the A-scan of this point the front- and backwall have to be identified by the computer on the time scale. Those time values are then used together with the number of layers of the plate to find the intervals in the time domain in which the system looks for peak amplitude values of the reflections, which then are stored in a computer file and afterwards processed to make coloured 2D-images of each interval.

The first procedure has the disadvantage that it uses a lot of computer memory, so the post-processing has to be done on a mainframe computer because large files have to be processed. The second procedure runs on the computer attached to the C-scan system and cannot produce quasi-3D-plots of the information. Instead 2D-images for different time intervals can be put next to each other. For the latter procedure those 2D-images can be zoomed in and coloured according to the information given.

X-ray radiographs (when needed penetrant enhanced) were taken from each specimen to check the information obtained by the high frequency C-scan procedures.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The $(0^\circ, 90^\circ)_4$ carbon-epoxy laminate studied contained four square Tygavac foil inserts at each corner at different depths. An X-ray radiograph was taken to find the lateral position of the inserts after production of the plate and a low frequency (10 MHz) C-scan was also carried out. The histogram of the peak amplitudes reflected from the glass plate placed behind the composite is given in figure 1. Studying this histogram one can choose thresholds for black and white C-scan pictures: the level 1 threshold gives the best indication of the lateral position of the inserts and even indicates that the lower right corner insert has a spot of better bonding with the surrounding composite layers.

The high frequency C-scan of this plate was carried out following the first procedure. The scan step in X en Y direction was 0.5 mm. The histogram of the times of flight of the different reflections from the composite plate is given in figure 2; the times of flight of the front- and backwall reflections of the plate are easily identified on this histogram. The mainframe computer consequently could make the quasi-3D plot of the composite plate knowing the mean difference in time of flight between the front- and backwall reflections and the number of layers of the composite plate (namely 8). The computer looked for peak amplitude values above a certain threshold in seven time of flight intervals ($x \pm 3$ time pulses). This plot is given in figure 3 and for each time interval section the amplitudes of the reflections have a certain grey value (see legend). The different inserts at the corners can be identified. Compared to the low frequency C-scan now the depth of the inserts can be deduced: top 2D-

image front-wall reflections, second 2D-image reflections from the region between the first layer and the second layer with one insert, etc. It must however be said that due to multiple reflections of the ultrasound in the composite plate, having layers of equal thicknesses, some inserts are indicated in other layers too, but the amplitude information is weaker and therefore decisive.

The $(\pm 45^\circ, 90^\circ, 0^\circ)_s$ carbon-epoxy laminate plate discussed in this paper was impacted. The interior damage state of this specimen was analysed by taking an X-ray radiograph and by making an high frequency ultrasonic C-scan following procedure two. The X-ray picture is given in figure 4, no depth information can be obtained for the different delaminations formed during the impact test. The high frequency ultrasonic C-scan was carried out using a step of 0.16 mm in the X and Y direction of scanning. Processing the amplitudes of the reflections measured in 7 intervals for this 8 layer quasi-isotropic composite gives the 2D-images of figure 5. The first delamination appearing is positioned between the top 90° and 0° composite layers. This information is still present in the lower layer-interfaces due to multiple reflections in the composite of the delamination reflection peaks. The next real delamination depicted is situated between the 0° and 90° composite layers and finally also a real delamination shows up between the -45° and $+45^\circ$ composite bottom layers.

This depth information of the different delaminations and the clear 2D-images of the different delaminations, can be used to find the most critical delaminations and to calculate the total delamination area, which then can be used in impact damage models for composites.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The high frequency ultrasonic C-scan technique and dataprocessing procedures discussed in this paper give detailed information on the artificial and impact damage present in carbon-epoxy composite laminates. The lateral and in depth resolution is highly satisfying, and gives engineers numbers to calculate with.

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References

1. A. Claeys, Hoogfrequente ultrasone C-scan: dataverwerking van ultrasone geluidssignalen van composieten (tekst en figuren), Master Thesis, Department of Metallurgy and Materials Engineering, 1989-1990.
2. W. Van Dael, Schadeonderzoek in gelaagde composieten met hoogfrequente ultrasone geluidsgolven (deel 1 en 2), Master Thesis, Department of Metallurgy and Materials Engineering, 1990 - 1991.
3. T. Märtens, Analyse van impactschade in koolstof-epoxy laminaten met hoge resolutie ndt-technieken, Master Thesis, Department of Metallurgy and Materials Engineering, 1991-1992.

Figures

Fig. 1 Peak amplitude histogram and black and white C-scan pictures for different thresholds for the $(0^\circ, 90^\circ)_4$ carbon-epoxy laminate with artificial defects (low frequency C-scan)

Fig. 2 The histogram of the times of flight for the high frequency C-scan of the $(0^\circ, 90^\circ)_4$ carbon-epoxy laminate with artificial defects.

Fig. 3 Quasi 3D-plot for the high frequency C-scan of the $(0^\circ, 90^\circ)_4$ carbon-epoxy laminate with artificial defects.

Fig. 4 X-ray radiograph of the impacted ($\pm 45^\circ, 90^\circ, 0^\circ$)_s carbon-epoxy laminate.

Damage patterns at different depths

Carbon-epoxy plate 1mm thick
impacted at 1.4J

Legende

Schaal = 2

- | | |
|----------------|--------------------|
| Amplitude < 39 | ■ Amplitude < 91 |
| Amplitude < 56 | ■ Amplitude < 108 |
| Amplitude < 74 | ■ Amplitude >= 108 |

Fig. 5 2D-images for different times of flight intervals of the high frequency ultrasonic C-scan of the impacted ($\pm 45^\circ, 90^\circ, 0^\circ$)_s carbon-epoxy laminate.